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DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION OF LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF OMBITASVIR, PARITAPREVR AND RITONAVIR IN FIXED TABLET DOSAGE FORM

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ABSTRACT

Technivie® is a fixed-dose combination of ombitasvir, a hepatitis C virus NS5A inhibitor, paritaprevir, a hepatitis C virus NS3/4A protease inhibitor, and ritonavir, a CYP3A inhibitor and is indicated in combination with ribavirin for the treatment of patients with genotype-4 chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection without cirrhosis. Developing a single analytical method for the estimation of individual drugs in a quad pill is very challenging, due to the formation of drug-drug and drug-excipient interactions. The present study demonstrates the applicability of chromatographic method to develop a new, sensitive, single HPLC method for the simultaneous quantitative determination of four antiviral agents in fixed pharmaceutical dosage form. Chromatographic separation of the four antiviral drugs was achieved by using a gradient elution at a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min on Inertsil ODS 3V C18 column (250m×4.6mm, 5µm particle size, 100Å pore size) at ambient temperature. Mobile phase A of the gradient solvent system was KH₂PO₄ (0.03M) in 1000 ml of water and by adjusting the pH to 3.2 with dilute ortho-phosphoric acid and mobile phase B was Methanol and water in the ratio of 85:15 v/v. UV detection at 265 nm was employed to monitor the analytes. A linear response was observed for Paritaprevir over the concentration range 30–180 µg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 5-30µg/ mL of Ombitasvir and 20-120 µg/ mL Ritonavir. Limit of detection (LOD) for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir were 0.075µg/mL, 0.125µg/mL, 0.00575µg/mL and 3µg/mL respectively. Limit of quantification (LOQ) for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir were 0.225µg/mL, 0.375µg/mL, and 0.015µg/mL respectively.

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INTRODUCTION

TECHNIVIE® is a fixed-dose combination tablet containing ombitasvir, paritaprevir, and ritonavir for oral administration¹. Ombitasvir, paritaprevir, ritonavir fixed dose combination tablet includes a hepatitis-C virus NS5A inhibitor (ombitasvir), a hepatitis-C virus NS3/4A protease inhibitor (paritaprevir), and a CYP3A inhibitor (ritonavir) that inhibits CYP3A mediated metabolism of paritaprevir, thereby providing increased plasma concentration of paritaprevir². The chemical name of ombitasvir is Dimethyl ((2S,5S)-1-(4-tert-butylphenyl) pyrrolidine-2,5-diyl)bis{benzene-4,1-diylcarbonyl(2S)pyrrolidine-2,1-diyl[(2S)-3-methyl-1-oxobutane-1,2-diyl]}biscarbamate hydrate³. The molecular formula is C₅₀H₆₇N₇O₈•4.5H₂O (hydrate) and the molecular weight for the drug substance is 975.20 (hydrate). The drug substance is white to light yellow to light pink powder, and is practically insoluble in aqueous buffers but is soluble in ethanol⁴. The chemical name of paritaprevir is (2R,6S,12Z,13aS,14aR,16aS)-N-(cyclopropylsulfonyl)-6-[(5-methylpyrazin-2-yl)carbonyl]amino}-5, 16-dioxo-2-(phenanthridin-6-yloxy) 1,2,3,6,7,8,9,10, 11,13a,14,15,16-tetra deca hydro cyclo propa [e]pyrrolo[1,2-a][1,4] diazacyclo pentadecine-14a(5H)-carboxamide dihydrate. The molecular formula is C₄₀H₄₃N₇O₇S•2H₂O (dihydrate) and the molecular weight for the drug substance is 801.91 (dihydrate). The drug substance is white to off-white powder with very low water solubility⁵. The chemical name of ritonavir is [5S-(5R*,8R*,10R*,11R*)]10-Hydroxy-2-methyl-5-(1-methylethyl)-1-[2-(1-methylethyl)-4-thiazolyl]-3,6-dioxo-8,11-bis(phenylmethyl)-2,4,7,12-tetraazatridecane-13-oic acid,5-thiazolylmethyl ester⁶. The molecular formula is C₃₇H₄₈N₆O₅S₂ and the molecular weight for the drug substance is 720.95. The drug substance is white to off white to light tan powder practically insoluble in water and freely soluble in methanol and ethanol^{7,8}.

A survey of literature has revealed several analytical methods for the determination of ombitasvir and Paritaprevir in combination with Ritonavir in bio-logical fluids and in pharmaceutical products. These include; high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)⁹. On the contrary, to the best of our knowledge, there is no method reporting the simultaneous determination of Ombitasvir, paritaprevir, ritonavir in fixed pharmaceutical formulation. In this paper, we report the simple precise and accurate RP-HPLC method for the assay of Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir in fixed dosage form. The new method is capable of separating all four active ingredients present in the tablet. Validation of the current method will be performed according to the requirements of USP for assay determination which include accuracy, precision, selectivity, linearity and range.

Figure-1: Chemical structures of Ombitasvir, Ritonavir, and Paritaprevir.

Experimental:

Chemicals and reagents:

Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir, and Ritonavir are obtained as kind gift samples from Mylan laboratories Ltd, Hyderabad. Potassium dihydrogen ortho-phosphate, methanol, acetonitrile and ortho-phosphoric acid were obtained from Merck, Mumbai, India. All the solutions were prepared in Milli Q water (Millipore, USA). Test samples composed of Technivie® film-coated fixed dose tablet contains 150 mg of Ombitasvir, 150 mg of Ritonavir; 200 mg of Paritaprevir are obtained from Gilead Sciences, Kaulalampur, Malaysia.

HPLC Instrumentation and Chromatographic conditions:

Waters Alliance 2695 separation module (Waters Corporation, Milford, USA) equipped with 2489 UV/visible detector or 2998 PDA detector with Empower 2 software was used for the analysis. The HPLC system was equipped with a column compartment with temperature control and an on-line degasser. Inertsil ODS 3V C18 column (250×4.6mm, 5µm, Waters Corporation, Milford, USA) and a gradient mixture of solvent A and B were used as stationary and mobile phases, respectively. Buffer contains 4.08 gms of Potassium Dihydrogen Orthophosphate (0.03M) in 1000 ml of water and by adjusting its pH was adjusted to 3.2 with ortho-phosphoric acid. Buffer was used as solvent A. Methanol and water in the ratio of 85:15 (v/v) was used as solvent B. The gradient program (T/%B) was given in Table-1, was adjusted at 1.0 ml/min flow rate and 20 µL injection volume were maintained. The eluted compounds were monitored at 265 nm. The column oven temperature was maintained at 25 °C. Data acquisition, analysis, and reporting were performed by Empower2 (Waters) chromatography software.

Table-1 Gradient program for the elution of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir and Ombitasvir.

Time	Mobile phase-A	Mobile phase-B
0	90	10
3	90	10
4	30	70
6	10	90
11	10	90
13	90	10
15	90	10

Preparation of Solutions:**Standard and stock solutions:**

Standard solution of the three active ingredients of the drug was prepared in the following manner: Transfer 25 mg of Ombitasvir, 100 mg of Ritonavir and 150 mg of Paritaprevir working standards into a 100 ml volumetric flask, dissolve and dilute with Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 as diluent. 5 ml of the resulting solution is further diluted up to 50 ml in volumetric flask with diluents. The resulting solution contains 150 µg/mL of Paritaprevir, 100 µg/mL of Ritonavir and 25µg/mL of the Ombitasvir as working standard solutions. The prepared stock solutions were stored at 4 °C and protected from light.

Preparation of the Sample solution:

Twenty tablets were weighed and their average weight was calculated. The tablets were crushed to a homogeneous powder and a quantity equivalent to one tablet (600.2mg) was weighed and transferred in to a 100-mL volumetric flask, extracted in diluent by sonication, and filtered through Whatman no. 41 filter paper. The filtrate (5 mL) was quantitatively transferred to a 50-mL volumetric flask, and solution was diluted to volume with the diluents.

Solutions for validation study:**Calibration and Quality control samples:**

Calibration standards (30–180 µg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 5-30µg/ mL of Ombitasvir and 20-120 µg/ mL Ritonavir were prepared from working standard solutions by appropriate dilution with Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 as diluents. Quality control (QC) samples for accuracy studies were prepared at three concentrations of the linearity range (120 µg/ mL, 150 µg/ mL and 180 µg/ mL) for Paritaprevir, (20 µg/ mL, 25 µg/ mL and 30 µg/ mL) for Ombitasvir and (80 µg/ mL, 100 µg/ mL and 120 µg/ mL) for Ritonavir were prepared from the standard solutions.

Method Validation:

The developed chromatographic method was validated for selectivity, linearity, precision, accuracy, sensitivity, robustness and system suitability.

Specificity:

The terms selectivity and specificity are often used interchangeably. The specificity of the developed LC method for quantification of all the four drugs was determined in the presence of excipients present in pharmaceutical products. In specificity study, interference between drugs and tablet excipients were evaluated from the comparison of spectral purity obtained from the analysis for the standard solutions and sample solutions.

System suitability:

The system suitability was assessed by six replicate analyses of the drugs at concentrations of 150 µg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 100 µg/ mL for Ritonavir and 25 µg/ mL each for Ombitasvir. The acceptance criterion was ±2% for the RSD for the peak area and retention times for all four analytes. The system suitability parameters with respect to theoretical plates, tailing factor, repeatability and resolution between Paritaprevir peak and peaks of the other three analytes were defined.

Linearity:

Linearity of the method was evaluated at six equi-spaced concentration levels by diluting the standard solutions to give solutions over the ranges 20–120% target concentration for all three analytes respectively. The calibration curves were constructed at six concentrations between 30–180 µg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 5-30µg/ mL of Ombitasvir and 20-120 µg/ mL Ritonavir. These were injected in triplicate and the peak areas were inputted into a Microsoft Excel® spreadsheet program to plot calibration curves. The linearity was evaluated by linear regression analysis, which was calculated by the least square regression method. The peak areas of the drugs to drugs concentration were used for plotting the linearity graph. The linearity data is reported in Table-3.

Table-3: Linearity Data of Paritaprevir, Ritonavir and Ombitasvir

Precision:

Precision was evaluated in terms of intra-day repeatability and inter-day reproducibility. The intra-day repeatability was investigated using six separate sample solutions prepared, as reported above, from the freshly reconstructed tablet formulations at 100% of the target level. Each solution was injected in triplicate and the peak areas obtained were used to calculate means and RSD% values. The inter-day reproducibility was, by preparing and analyzing in triplicate sample solutions from the reconstructed formulations at the same concentration level of intra-day repeatability; the means and RSD% values were calculated from peak areas. (Table-4)

Table-4: Intra-day and inter-day precision data for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir, Ritonavir

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the method was determined by measuring the recovery of the drugs by the method of standard additions. Quality control (QC) samples for accuracy studies were prepared at three concentrations of the linearity range (120 µg/ mL (80% dilution), 150 µg/ mL (100% dilution) and 180 µg/ mL (120% dilution) for Paritaprevir, (20 µg/ mL (80% dilution), 25 µg/ mL (100% dilution) and 30 µg/ mL (120% dilution) for Ombitasvir and (80 µg/ mL (80% dilution) , 100 µg/ mL (100% dilution) and 120 µg/ mL (120% dilution) for Ritonavir were prepared from the standard solutions. Known amounts of 10 % dilution of each drug corresponding to 80%, 100%, and 120% of the target test concentrations (50 µg/mL of Paritaprevir, 10 µg/mL of Ritonavir and 2.5µg/mL of Ombitasvir) were added to a placebo mixture to determine whether the excipients present in the formulation led to positive or negative interferences. Each set of additions was repeated three times at each level. Extraction sample preparation procedure is followed and assayed against qualified reference standard. The accuracy was expressed as the percentage of the analytes re-covered by the assay. (Table-5)

Table-5: Accuracy: recovery data for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir, and Ritonavir

Sensitivity:

Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were estimated from the signal- to-noise ratio. The detection limit was determined as the lowest concentration level resulting in a peak area of three times the baseline noise. The limit of detection was determined, by injecting progressively low concentrations of four analytes of interest. The quantification limit was determined as the lowest concentration level that provided a peak area with signal-to-noise 10.

Robustness:

To determine the robustness of the developed method, experimental conditions were deliberately changed and the relative standard deviation for replicate injections of Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir peaks and the USP resolution factor between Paritaprevir and the other two peaks were evaluated. The mobile phase flow rate was 1.0 mL/min. This was changed by ±0.2 units to 0.8 and 1.2 mL/min. The effect of stationary phase was studied by the use of LC columns from different batches at 25°C. The effect of buffer pH was studied at pH 3.0 and 3.4 (± 0.2 units). The chromatographic variations were evaluated for resolution between Paritaprevir and the other three analytes in a system suitability solution with respect to retention time RT and % assay of drugs.

Solution stability:

To assess the solution stability, standard and test solutions were kept at 25 °C (laboratory temperature) for 24 h. These solutions were compared with freshly prepared standard and test solutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**HPLC method development:**

All the three drug solutions were prepared in diluent at a concentration of 100µg/mL and scanned in UV-Visible spectrometer; all the drugs were having UV maxima at around 265 nm. Hence detection at 265 nm was selected for method development purpose. Some important parameters, pH of the mobile phase, concentration of the acid or buffer solution, percentage and type of the organic modifier, etc. were tested for a good chromatographic separation. The main analytical challenge during development of a new method was obtaining adequate retention of the polar parent compounds Paritaprevir and Ombitasvir while maintaining a reasonable elution time for the less-polar Ritonavir. Trials showed that acidic mobile phase with reverse phase column gives symmetric and sharp peaks. For this reason, potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer with pH-3.2 was adjusted with *o*-phosphoric acid was preferred as acidic buffer solution. Methanol and water in the ratio of 85:15 was chosen as the organic modifier because it dissolves drugs very well. Mobile phase composition in gradient mode at a flow rate of 1.0 mL per minute was observed for a good resolution. Then method was optimized to separate all the active ingredients by changing to Gradient mode. Several gradient conditions were tried before optimizing the final gradient program as: time (min)/% solution B: 0/10, 3/10, 4/70, 6/90, 11/90, 13/10 and 15/10. The satisfactory chromatographic separation, with good peak shapes were achieved on Inertsil ODS 3V-C18 (250 × 4.6) mm with 5 µm particles, using the column temperature as maintained at 35°C and the detection was monitored at a wavelength of 240 nm. The injection volume was 20 µL. Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 v/v) were used as diluent. In the optimized gradient conditions Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir, and Ritonavir were well separated with a resolution (Rs) of greater than 2 and the typical retention times of Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir, and Ritonavir were about 6.275, 10.445 and 8.45 respectively, the typical chromatogram of System suitability shown in Figure 2.

Method validation:

The developed method was validated, as described below, for the following parameters: system suitability, selectivity, linearity, precision, accuracy and LOD/LOQ.

Selectivity:

Selectivity of the current method was demonstrated by good separation of the four active ingredients (Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir). Furthermore, matrix components, e.g. excipients, do not interfere with the four analytes as they have no absorbance. The representative chromatogram (Fig. 5A) of the fixed dosage form solution containing excipients showed no peak interfering with analytes; moreover the adjacent chromatographic peaks were separated with resolution factors >3. Overall, these data demonstrated that the excipients did not interfere with the active ingredients peaks, indicating selectivity of the method

System suitability:

The RSD values of peak area and retention time for the analytes are within 2% indicating the suitability of the system.

Figure-2: System suitability chromatogram of combined standard solution contains 150 μg/mL of Paritaprevir, 100 μg/mL of Ritonavir and 25μg/mL of the Ombitasvir as working standard solutions.

Table-2: Results of System suitability study.

Parameter	Ombitasvir	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir
Retention time	8.45 (min)	6.3 (min)	10.5 (min)
Theoretical plates	52314.95	60827.78	29853.10
Tailing Factor	1.14	1.10	1.08
HETP	4.7787×10 ⁻⁶	4.1099×10 ⁻⁶	8.375×10 ⁻⁶
USP plates/meter	209260	243312	119412.40
Resolution	16.58	---	10.22
Peak area	8210788	7795456	2349099
% of Peak area	44.99	42.18	12.83

Linearity and range:

Six concentration levels within 20–120% of the target concentration range for analytes were considered to study the linearity. The calibration curves were prepared by plotting the peak area of the drug to the respective concentrations, which were linear in the range of 20–240μg/ mL for Paritaprevir, 30–360μg/ mL for and 15-180 μg/ mL each of Ombitasvir and cobicistat. Peak areas of the active ingredients and concentrations were subjected to least square linear regression analysis to calculate the calibration equations and correlation coefficients. The mean regression equations were found as $y=103089.274x+ 25571.2$ for ombitasvir, $y=50825x+ 318405.6667$ for Paritaprevir and $y=80344.151x+ 386346.4$ for Ritonavir. The square of the correlation coefficient ($r^2 > 0.999$) demonstrated a significant correlation between the concentration of analytes and detector response. The results show that there is an excellent correlation between the peak area ratios and the concentrations of drugs in the range tested.

Table-3: Linearity data for the Technivie®-fixed dosage form.

Parameter	Ombitasvir	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir
Concentration Range	5-30 µg/mL	30-180 µg/mL	20-120 µg/mL
Regression equation	$Y = 103089.274x + 25571.2$	$Y = 50825x + 318405.6667$	$Y = 80344.151x + 386346.4$
Correlation Coefficient	0.9999	0.9999	0.9999
Limit of Detection (LOD)	0.125 µg/mL	0.075 µg/mL	0.005 µg/mL
Limit of Quantification (LOQ)	0.375 µg/mL	0.225 µg/mL	0.015 µg/mL

Figure-3: Calibration Curves of Ombitasvir, Paritaprevir and Ritonavir standard solutions.**Precision:**

Precision of this method was determined by injecting the standard solution of the three analytes six times. The R.S.D. of peak area of six replicates was found to be less than 2. The results obtained are shown in Table 4. In all instances the %RSD values were less than 2%.

Table-4: Intra-day and inter-day precision data for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir.

Analyte	% of the target concentration (µg/mL)	Intra-day Variation (%RSD)	Inter-day Variation (%RSD)
Paritaprevir	100 % (150 µg/mL)	0.7 (n=6)	0.4 (n=6)
Ombitasvir	100 % (25 µg/mL)	0.6 (n=6)	0.3 (n=6)
Ritonavir	100 % (100 µg/mL)	0.3 (n=6)	0.6 (n=6)

Accuracy:

Percentage recovery of the four active ingredients using this method was determined using the fixed dose combination tablet dosage forms. The results of accuracy studies from standard solution and excipient matrix were shown in Table 5; recovery values demonstrated that the method was accurate within the desired range.

Table-5: Accuracy: recovery data for Paritaprevir, Ritonavir and Ombitasvir.

Accuracy study at 80% target level	Injection Number	Ombitasvir	Ritonavir	Paritaprevir
Technivie® Film coated fixed dose tablet solution at 80% level was spiked with 10% of mixed standard solution of API's	1	2533880	7774879	7437248
	2	2517336	7771214	7447335
	3	2521981	7748273	7456848
	Mean area	2524399.0	7764788.7	7447143.7
	Std. Dev	8532.9	14419.9	9801.4
	% RSD	0.3	0.2	0.1
	% Recovery	103.80	99.91	90.83
Accuracy study at 100% target level	Injection Number	Ombitasvir	Ritonavir	Paritaprevir
Technivie® Film coated fixed dose tablet solution solution at 100% level was spiked with 10% of mixed standard solution of API's	1	3059527	9765464	9204901
	2	3016088	9721710	9166530
	3	3044262	9614494	9232049
	Mean area	3039959.0	9700556	9201160.0
	Std. Dev	22036.9	77676.3	32919.3
	% RSD	107.00	0.8	0.4
	% Recovery		96.58	100.66
Accuracy study at 120% target level	Injection Number	Ombitasvir	Ritonavir	Paritaprevir
Technivie® Film coated fixed dose tablet solution solution at 120% level was spiked with 10% of mixed standard solution of API's	1	3587730	11252343	10678017
	2	3639051	11354176	10720290
	3	3420358	10844640	10312903
	Mean area	3549046.333	11150386.33	10570403.3
	Std. Dev	114363.4	269635.1	224001.3
	% RSD	3.2	2.4	2.1
	% Recovery	103.33	96.75	95.41

Sensitivity:

Limit of detection (LOD) for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir were 0.075µg/mL, 0.125µg/mL, 0.00575µg/mL and 3µg/mL respectively. Limit of quantification (LOQ) for Paritaprevir, Ombitasvir and Ritonavir were 0.225µg/mL, 0.375µg/mL, and 0.015µg/mL respectively. The results of LOD and LOQ were indicating a high sensitivity of the method.

Robustness:

The HPLC parameters were deliberately varied from normal procedural conditions including the mobile phase flow rate was 1.0 mL/min. This was changed by ±0.2 units to 0.8 and 1.2 mL/min. The effect of stationary phase was studied by the use of LC columns from different batches at 35°C. The effect of buffer pH was studied at pH 2.3 and 2.7 (± 0.2 units). Under these variations, all analytes were adequately resolved and elution orders remained unchanged. The testing solution maintained a signal-to-noise ratio over 10 in all varied conditions. The peak resolution between Paritaprevir and other three analytes were all larger than 1.5 under each variation.

Analysis of the fixed dose combination tablet:

Twenty tablets contents were accurately weighed, their mean weight were determined, and they were then finely powdered. An amount of the homogenous powder equivalent to one tablet (600.2 mg) was transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, added 40 ml of diluents (Acetonitrile and Buffer in the ratio of 70:30 v/v), sonicated for 30 min, diluted to 100 ml with methanol and a 5ml sample taken from this solution was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min. A 1-ml aliquot from supernatant was then decanted to another 10-ml volumetric flask. Test solutions were then made up to volume with the mobile phase. The amounts of Ritonavir, Paritaprevir and Ombitasvir in ternary mixtures or dosage forms were individually calculated using the related linear regression equations.

On the basis of above results, the proposed method was applied to the simultaneous determination of three antiviral drugs present in fixed dosage forms which comprised the ternary mixture (Technivie® film-coated tablet contains 25 mg of Ombitasvir, 100 mg of Ritonavir and 150 mg of Paritaprevir). Figure-3 shows representative chromatograms obtained from the analysis of Technivie® tablets. The differences between the amount claimed and those assayed were very low and the R.S.D. values were within the acceptable range mentioned by pharmacopoeias. The mean percentage recoveries obtained after six repeated experiments were found between 97.53 and 100.98 (Table 6), indicating that the results are accurate and precise and there is no interference from the common excipients used in the pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Table-6: Assay results of Paritaprevir (PRT), Ritonavir (RTV) and Ombitasvir (OBV) in tablets.

Formulation	Label Claim (mg/tablet)			Amount found in (mg)		
	Ombitasvir	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir	Ombitasvir	Paritaprevir	Ritonavir
Technivie® is a fixed-dose combination tablet	25 mg	150 mg	100 mg	24.85	148 mg	98.68

Figure-3: A typical Chromatogram of pharmaceutical fixed dosage form (Technivie® tablets).

CONCLUSION

In this study, a validated simple and reliable RP-HPLC-PDA procedure was described for the assay of a complex multi drug combination consisting of Ombitasvir, Ritonavir, Paritaprevir, and DF for oral administration which is indicated as one-pill, once-a-day prescription medicine used as a complete HIV-1 treatment. To our present knowledge, no attempts have yet been made to estimate this multidrug mixture by analytical procedure. All the four active ingredients were successfully resolved and quantified using Inertsil ODS 3V C18 column (250×4.6mm, 5µm) in a relatively short run time of 18 minutes in gradient mode of chromatographic method. The proposed method provides a good resolution between active ingredients. The developed method reported herein was validated by parameters as described in ICH-Q2B guideline. System suitability, specificity, linearity, LOD, LOQ values, within- and between-day precision and accuracy of the proposed technique were obtained during the validation studies. The proposed method has the advantages of simplicity, repeatability, sensitivity and requires less expensive reagents.

REFERENCES

1. Viekira pakTM (ombitasvir, paritaprevir and ritonavir tablets; dasabuvir tablets), for oral Use. Full prescribing information (PDF). AbbVie Inc., North Chicago, IL 60064. Revised 30 July 2015 22 International Journal of Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry 2017; 7(1): 12-2
2. FDA approves Viekira pak to treat hepatitis C". Food and Administration. December 19, 2014.
3. TECHNIVIE® (ombitasvir, paritaprevir and ritonavir) Tablets", for oral Use. Full prescribing information (PDF). AbbVie Inc., North Chicago, IL 60064. Retrieved 28 July 2015 Seng-Lai Tan; Yupeng He, eds. (2011). Hepatitis C: antiviral drug discovery and development. Norfolk: Caister academic press. p. 210. ISBN 9781904455783. Retrieved 28 April 2014
4. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. United States: New approved drugs, Inc.; c2007-08. Available from: <http://www.aegis.org/news/fda/2009/FD090901.html> [Last updated on 2008 Sep 4; cited 2011 Oct 9]
5. Donald Jensen; Nancy Reau, eds. (2013). Hepatitis C. New York: Oxford University Press. p. 144. ISBN 9780199844296. Retrieved 28 April 2014.
6. Kowdley, Kris V.; Lawitz, Eric; Poordad, Fred; Cohen, Daniel E.; Nelson, David R.; Zeuzem, Stefan; Everson, Gregory T.; Kwo, Paul; Foster, Graham R.; Sulkowski, Mark S.; Xie, Wangang; Pilot-Matias, Tami; Liou, George; Larsen, Lois; Khatri, Amit; Podsadecki, Thomas; Bernstein, Barry (2014). "Phase 2b Trial of Interferon-free Therapy for Hepatitis C Virus Genotype 1". New England Journal of Medicine. 370 (3): 222–232. Doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa11306227. ISSN 0028-4793.
7. Stefan Mauss; et al., eds. (2013). Hepatology 2013 a clinical textbook (PDF) (4th ed.). Dusseldorf: Flying Publisher. ISBN 978-3-924774-90-5. Retrieved 28 April 2014.
8. Ritonavir. The American Society of Health-System Pharmacists". Retrieved Oct 23, 2015.
9. Alessandra Ariaudo^{a,1}, Fabio Favata^{a,1}, Amedeo De Nicolò^{a,*1}, Marco Simiele^{a,b}, Luca Paglietti^a, Lucio Boglione^a, Chiara Simona Cardellino^a, Chiara Carcieri^a, Giovanni Di Perri^{a,1}, Antonio D'Avolio^{a,1}. Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis 125 (2016) 369–375.

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